

BigStuff 07 Presentation 26/06/07 V6 Training of Volunteers in Aviation Conservation

Brian Barker, Imperial War Museum
bbarker@iwm.org.uk

Good afternoon Ladies & Gentlemen. As you can see from the screen my name is Brian Barker. I'm from the UK and I am based at the Imperial War Museum, Duxford.

The museum, which is now Europe's premier aviation Museum, started life as an airfield during the 1st World War and then played a vital role in the 2nd World War. Initially as a Royal Air Force fighter station and then as an American fighter base. Today it is home to some 200+ exhibits and attracts visitors from around the world and in particular from the USA.

In the UK we have probably the largest collection of heritage aircraft in Europe. These are spread out at over 60 different locations ranging from collections like Duxford to collections where one aircraft is situated in a car park. Unfortunately the standards of care and preservation vary on the same scale as the size of the collections.

Most of these sites are operated and managed by volunteers many of whom have no employment background in aviation. What they lack in knowledge they make up for in enthusiasm.

Unfortunately, in many cases, enthusiasm is not enough:

For example, a Vulcan BMk2 aircraft, having been decommissioned by the Royal Air Force was flown into Blackpool Airport in 1983 – the aircraft had been obtained by a group of enthusiasts with the expressed intention of keeping it fully maintained and possibly in flying condition. This well-meaning group did not have the expertise to achieve their aim. Reportedly they failed to obtain any of the technical publications relevant to the aircraft nor did they purchase any spare parts even though they were in plentiful supply at that time.

Very little happened to the aircraft and given that Blackpool is a seaside location the heavily laden salt air soon started its inevitable destruction work. Despite several attempts to rescue it the object fell into a very bad state of repair. Eventually it became so dangerous that in 2006 it had to be sold for scrap!

This incident was not an isolated one and more exhibits are in danger of going the same way. To counter this the British Aviation Preservation Council – the body that links all of the aviation heritage organisations – formed a partnership with the Imperial War Museum, Duxford to attempt to redress the situation.

Together they were successful in obtaining a grant from the Heritage Lottery Fund which was to be used for providing training to BAPC volunteers in the conservation and preservation of non-flying aviation heritage exhibits.

(It is important to note here the distinction between flying and non-flying aviation heritage aircraft. All heritage aircraft that are actually flown must be maintained to standards set by National Aviation Authorities and as a consequence are in a condition that is far from the original standard).

Using the funds the partnership set up the **National Aviation Heritage Skills Initiative**. This was a groundbreaking project – the first of its kind in the UK and probably in Europe as well. Based on the original funding application the project was to have a life span of 5 years until Dec 2009.

The primary aim of the Initiative was to improve standards of conservation within the aviation heritage sector. Within the original application this was expressed as:

1. To design suitable training for volunteers in the conservation & preservation of aircraft.
2. To gain national accreditation for the training courses.
3. To provide that training, on site at Duxford and at BAPC member organisations across the UK.
4. To widen the volunteer participation base.

I am here today to tell you something about how we got started, what we have achieved so far and where we hope to go in the future.

My role in this is as the Project Co-ordinator. I was recruited for the position having served 28 years in the Royal Air Force as an aircraft technician of which 8 years were directly involved in engineering training. The rest of the team consists of an Administrator who was seconded from the Museum, and 2 Instructors. The instructors are also both ex-Royal Air Force technicians with extensive experience in training; additionally one of the instructors had previously worked at the museum for 10 years as an Assistant Conservation Manager.

We formed up in July 2005. The first thing we had to do was develop a training strategy. This we did with reference to the Training Needs Analysis that had been carried out as part of the application process. What they did was send out questionnaires to both individual volunteers and to the management teams of the various organisations. The responses to these were carefully analysed and then presented to the Heritage Lottery Fund as justification for the training Programme. Having studied the application the training team found that there were a number of important constraints and factors that would impact on our decisions:

1. Training courses could not be longer than 1 day – volunteers said that was as much time as they were willing to give up to attend.
2. Training sessions must be available on any day of the week including Saturdays and Sundays.
3. Where possible training would be provided on site at the various member organisations.
4. Volunteers must be given the choice as to whether or not they wish to be assessed – it could not be mandatory.

Having taken into account these constraints and having closely examined the questionnaire responses and how they related to perceived areas where lack of knowledge was a factor we finally developed an initial Training Strategy.

Being experienced trainers and course designers we realised that this was just a starting point. It is important to recognise that the design process of any form of training must be the subject of constant review and testing to ensure that it remains appropriate and relevant.

If we jump ahead you can see from the date at the top this Training Strategy reflects the current position but as with all things in training every thing is subject to change. I think this is currently Version 12!! Fundamentally it's the same as Version 1 other than this one contains slightly more training modules because we found during the design stage that some subjects needed to be split in two. In addition we have introduced a series of presentations that are aimed at management level groups, typically these will last for approx 2 – 3 hours.

Another major decision that we had to make was the method of delivering the training. It had to be a consideration that the majority of volunteers in the aviation heritage sector are males over the age of 65. For the classroom elements we decided that participation in an interactive session with the instructor leading the conversation was the most successful method. During testing of the modules we tried the traditional 'chalk & talk' method where the instructor virtually lectures the audience but it was not at all popular. Given our chosen instructional format we decided to limit the class size to eight students; our experience said that an instructor could keep 8 involved but with any more someone might get lost in the crowd.

To support this style of delivery we put a great deal of effort into producing extremely comprehensive Training Notes with the intention that these would become reference documents for the future.

During the initial Course Design phase I made a point of going to various BAPC meetings and other organisations to advertise our activities and also to ensure that the team did not stray from the 'grass roots' requirement. We also produced brochures and posters which we distributed in order to keep the interest of our intended audience.

As part of the Training Strategy we produced a Volunteer's Log Book. These have since become exceptionally popular and volunteers are keen to show others the contents of their book:

Section 1 records all the training undertaken through this project.

Section 2 is for other forms of external training such as First Aid or possibly Fork-Lift Driving.

Section 3 of the handbook is probably a bit controversial. This allows organisations to document the activities that the individual is authorised to carry out. In our view organisations should authorise their volunteers to carry out certain tasks such as moving aircraft or operating various machines. In the UK under Health and Safety Regulations we believe this to be not just good practice but required practice. We have offered to assist any organisation that wishes to implement an authorisation process but does not have the necessary experience in such matters.

Finally Section 4 is marked 'Projects' and we encourage volunteers to record details of various aspects of conservation work that they have been involved in. This section has become a particular favourite and already we are seeing logbooks with some very impressive work records in them.

Another activity that started during the design phase was our bid to have our training accredited by an external educational body. Eventually we decided that City & Guilds was the most prestigious name that we could associate with our project.

Following many visits, much hard work and finally a full audit by City & Guilds staff we were accredited in May 2006. We now have to look forward to annual reviews to maintain our status.

As part of the City & Guilds accreditation we had to devise an Assessment strategy. Initially this was a bit of a problem. Things had changed dramatically from our time as trainers in the Royal Air Force where, in those days, assessment consisted of pass the examination or else!! We were very fortunate to secure the services of Cambridge Assessment, a commercial partner of Oxford, Cambridge and Royal Society of Arts examination Board. They gave us advice, ran a full day workshop and proof read our documentation – very fortunately all of this was free of charge thus I shall be eternally grateful. I am pleased to say that our subsequent assessment methodology met with the full approval of City & Guilds. We held our very first course at Duxford in April 2006. The initial feedback from the volunteers attending training was very positive. As the number of modules has increased we see the same faces coming back for more and they still seem very enthusiastic.

As the range of courses has developed we have now started instruction on practical skills such as aircraft skin repairs and the application of protective treatments and paint finishes. In this we have been extremely lucky in that the Imperial War Museum has allowed us to take over a small corner of the main conservation hanger where we can hold training sessions.

This development gave rise to a new set of problems. First the training sessions must be held at IWM Duxford because of the amount of specialist tooling required and in particular access to a high-pressure air supply to power pneumatic tools. We were aware that most organisations did not possess this capability but we were of the opinion it was pointless to train volunteers using incorrect tools such as electric drills. For example a cordless electrical drill operates at about 1000 – 1200 rpm whereas a pneumatic drill operates at around 2200 – 3000 rpm. This difference is considerable and has huge ramifications when drilling out rivets to effect a repair or replace a component. We took the view that it was vital to show volunteers the correct techniques so that we might be able to influence standards from the grass roots up.

The second decision we had to make was to reduce the class size to 4 volunteers and where necessary to use 2 instructors. We decided that given we only had one day to achieve a number of training objectives it would work best with 2 groups of 2 volunteers, working as a team and each team being supervised by a dedicated instructor.

As I said earlier the one consistent point about training is the rate of change. So as we push on with course design I am certain there will be further alterations to our Training Strategy and delivery style.

As you will probably have guessed we cannot hope to train qualified engineers in a series of 1-day sessions. Our primary aim is to instil into the volunteer workforce a sense of empathy for the objects they work on and to make them more preservation and conservation aware. We firmly believe that we will have succeeded if when asked to carry out a task on an exhibit the volunteer asks **WHY!**

Unfortunately it is a fact that in the aviation heritage sector many volunteer run organisations believe conservation and preservation to be based around stripping all the paint off an exhibit and then

presenting it in a shiny new livery. Admittedly there may be occasions when this is a valid course of action, sometimes a necessity but not every time.

Presuming that the **WHY** question is answered then we hope that whilst carrying out the task the volunteer gives due weight to the knowledge that he has acquired from our training.

So that gets us to where we think we are today – what of the future. Indeed you might recall I said at the beginning that this project has a 5-year life span and is in fact due to close in December 2009, so is there a future?

The BAPC, its members, the IWM and the team firmly believe that this project is too important to disappear. We are actively pursuing a number of avenues:

First we are approaching various bodies, both public and private, to seek additional funding.

Another option is to run the Training Centre at Duxford as a commercial venture. Already we have had expressions of interest from Canada, Greece and Australia to provide similar dealing.

We are also keen to diversify and run courses for organisations in different sectors of the Industrial Heritage world. We believe that much of our course content can be delivered, with only minor changes, to Industrial, Maritime and Vehicle Museums and other general collections in the UK and possibly Europe.

To sum up the aim of the Initiative is: To provide conservation and preservation training to volunteers working in the Aviation Heritage sector on non-flying aircraft and exhibits.

So how do we know if we have achieved the aim?

Well we have certainly provided training – from Course No.1 in 2006 up to the end of June 2007 we held 110 Training Sessions for 780 Volunteers, of whom 425 have registered for the assessment programme. These sessions have included 18 different BAPC member groups around the UK.

We gained City & Guilds accreditation in 2006 and successfully passed our 2007 annual review.

When practical we do provide the training anywhere in the UK.

What about Widening Participation and have we made a difference?

These elements are not for us, the team, to judge so we have recently arranged for an external evaluation of the programme to be carried out by the Institute of Conservation. Their report will provide an independent assessment of our project and could be crucial if we apply for further funding.

Certainly those volunteers who have attended the training courses seem to be of the opinion that we are succeeding.

Thank you for your kind attention.